

Studies on the Effect of Lifetime Variation on Magnetic Field Modulation of Exciplex Luminescence[†]

DEB NARAYAN NATH, SAMITA BASU and MIHIR CHOWDHURY

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 082

The lifetime of the pyrene-*N,N*-dimethylaniline exciplex luminescence with a fixed concentration of donor and acceptor has been varied by adding quenchers and/or changing solvents. Its effect on the magnetic field modulation of the exciplex luminescence has been studied. The results are discussed in the light of electron hopping theory and possible environmental perturbation on the ISC process occurring on the bi-radical pair.

THE magnetic field modulation of radical pair (r.p.) recombination in solution has become a subject of interest in recent years¹⁻⁵. The effect of magnetic field on inter-system crossing (ISC) has been extensively studied by probing the triplet state through delayed fluorescence⁷⁻⁹ and direct triplet absorption¹⁰⁻¹⁴ and also by probing the singlet state through exciplex luminescence^{15,16}. The observation of the increase of the half-width of the magnetic field effect ($B_{1/2}$) with increase in donor concentration has initiated intense theoretical studies on the role of electron hopping in spin dynamics¹⁷⁻¹⁹. It is suggested that electron hopping between different donor and acceptor sites in solutions reduces the lifetime of a fixed nuclear environment and causes an uncertainty broadening of the energy levels which couples with hyperfine coupling and Zeeman interaction to increase the effective $B_{1/2}$ ^{17,18}. In the above theoretical framework, the solvent has been assumed to affect only the diffusion kinetics of the process through its macro-properties, like viscosity, dielectric constant (ϵ) etc. and not the spin rephasing dynamics of the r.p. directly. In an earlier paper¹⁸ based on our results with isotopically substituted solvent and 3-component mixed donor systems, we have suggested a more direct role of the non-bonded surrounding molecules in the spin evolution process. On replacing CH_3OH by CD_3OD we have observed a decrement of $B_{1/2}$ value for pyrene and *N,N*-dimethylaniline (Py-DMA) model exciplex system ($[\text{Py}] = 10^{-4} M$; $[\text{DMA}] = 0.3 \times 10^{-2} M$) from 51 ± 2 to 45 ± 2 G. We have also found that addition of another donor DMT (having almost identical $B_{1/2}$ as DMA and with concentration same as that of DMA) in a Py-DMA exciplex system has the same effect on $B_{1/2}$ as that of doubling the DMA concentration although, the rate of exchange of electron between DMA and DMT is much lower compared to that between two DMA molecules¹⁶. These observations have led us to propose a tentative mechanism that the environment of the decaying exciplex can also modulate the ISC process through

solvent hyperfine interaction (HFI). An alternative explanation of the results based on the level broadening due to environmental effect on lifetime of the exciplex is however conceivable. It may be argued that addition of a second donor might quench the exciplex luminescence and reduce the lifetime causing an uncertainty broadening of the energy levels and thus an increment in $B_{1/2}$. In this paper we have explored this possibility of correlation of $B_{1/2}$ with the lifetime (τ). The negative correlation reinforces our contention that probably the environmental perturbation occurs directly on the spin-rephasing process.

Experimental

The experimental arrangement is very similar to the one used in previous experiments¹⁶. A stable Wien bridge oscillator with synchronous output followed by a 60 W variable power amplifier has been used as the a.c. source. The photomultiplier was cooled to 0° to increase the signal to noise ratio. Commercially available compounds of the highest quality were purified by zone refining (pyrene) and vacuum distillation (DMA, propan-1-ol). Spectra grade CH_3OH (Aldrich) was used without further distillation. CsCl and KI (E. Merck) were purified through crystallisation.

The test solutions were $10^{-4} M$ in pyrene and 0.27×10^{-2} and $6 \times 10^{-2} M$ in DMA. Quencher concentration was varied over 3×10^{-2} to $20 \times 10^{-2} M$. The mixed solvents were prepared by mixing CH_3OH and $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ at different volume ratios. All samples were kept in closed sample cell through which nitrogen gas was bubbled for 40 min to deoxygenate. The sample characteristics remained steady throughout the experimental time. The lifetime (τ) of the exciplex luminescence was measured with a Applied Photophysics nanosecond spectrofluorometer based on time correlated single photon counting technique. The flash lamp was operated with 1 atm pressure of nitrogen and the

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Fig. 1. Pump data, decay data and single exponential deconvolution fit for the system [Py]=0.1 mM, [DMA]=60 mM in the mixed solvent (methanol-propanol=2:1 (v/v), N₂ bubbled), Chisqr=1.08 ns/channel=0.164, τ=17.3 ns.

TABLE I—MEASURED B_{1/2} VALUES (±2 G) AND Δφ/φ VALUES FOR SYSTEMS WITH DIFFERENT LIFETIMES

DMA concn mM	Quencher concn. mM	Solvent	ε	τ ns	B _{1/2} G	$\frac{\Delta\phi}{\phi} \times 100$
2.7		CH ₃ OH	33	25.9	50	1.60
60		CH ₃ OH	33	9.2	70	2.11
60	KI 60	CH ₃ OH	>33	6	65	0.84
60	CsCl 30	CH ₃ OH	>33	6	66	0.82
60	KI 200	CH ₃ OH	>33	4.7		0.25
60		CH ₃ OH + C ₂ H ₅ OH (2:1)	28.6	17.3	69	2.24
60		CH ₃ OH with air (O ₂)	33	6		0

FWHM of the pump function was 1.8 ns. The decay data was deconvoluted by the Applied Photophysics deconvolution program DECON1. The τ value was measured at wavelength 540 nm and the B_{1/2} at 550 nm.

Results and Discussion

We have measured (i) the percentage change in luminescence intensity (Δφ/φ) on application of saturating magnetic field and (ii) the field at which

the change in luminescence intensity is half of the value reached on saturation (B_{1/2}), as a function of the lifetime of the exciplex. The lifetime has been varied by two methods, (i) by adding quenchers which collisionally deactivate the exciplex and (ii) by changing the dielectric constant (ε) of the solvent which changes the ionisation rate or ionisation equilibrium of the exciplex, thus affecting its luminescence yield. A typical decay curve is shown in Fig. 1 and our results are displayed in a comprehensive manner in Table 1.

The complete ISC process is shown in Scheme 1. The magnetic field induced increment of the exciplex luminescence ($\Delta\phi$) originates from those

Scheme 1. ISC process in a biradical pair.

specimen of radical pairs which are initially uncaged ($r > r_1$) and form luminescent exciplex (caged r.p.) only after a diffusive excursion conserving the spin state. In the absence of the external magnetic field a portion of the uncaged radical pairs undergoes ISC through HFI during geminate recombination, while in its presence the degeneracy is lifted causing reduction in $K_{ST}(B)$, and the rate of back-formation of the caged r.p. is strengthened. For this reason, the magnetic field sensitivity ($\Delta\phi/\phi$) is high in case of triplet absorption¹¹ or delayed fluorescence studies⁹ ($\approx 18\%$), but is very low in the present case of singlet luminescence ($\approx 2\%$). Quenchers cause a marked decrease in $\Delta\phi/\phi$, presumably because the collisional quenching is more effective in the case of uncaged radical pair in comparison with that in the caged ones, and hence, cause a faster decrease in the number of exciplex molecules formed by recombination of radical pairs (*i.e.* as measured by $\Delta\phi$) compared with the number of fluorescent exciplexes originally formed at $r < r_1$ (*i.e.* as measured by ϕ). This observation is in conformity with the previous qualitative observation that O_2 quenches the magnetic field effect faster than the luminescence (Table 1).

The dependence of exciplex luminescence ϕ and the relative magnetic field effect $\Delta\phi/\phi$ at a fixed strength ($H=240$ G) on the dielectric constant ϵ is shown in Fig. 2. The data is similar to the case of Py-DEA exciplex system as reported by Petrov and others¹⁵. While ϕ decreases monotonically with increase in ϵ , $\Delta\phi/\phi$ shows a maxima at intermediate dielectric constant ($\epsilon \approx 30$). As dielectric constant diminishes ($\epsilon < 30$) the r.p. tends to be more caged and the relative distance between them does not allow sufficient level degeneracy to cause ISC through HFI and hence, $\Delta\phi$ decreases. Whereas for increased ϵ , the formation of the caged luminescent exciplex from the uncaged r.p. decreases because of the increasing potential barrier (due to reorientation of the solvent molecule) and the lowering of the ion-pair dissociation limit¹⁵. This decrease is more rapid than that of the fluorescent exciplex which has formed directly ($r < r_1$) and so $\Delta\phi/\phi$ again decreases. Table 1 also shows a decrease in $\Delta\phi/\phi$ on decreasing donor concentration; this is

Fig. 2. Dependence of exciplex fluorescence yield ϕ and the relative magnetic field effect $\Delta\phi/\phi$ (broken curve) at a field strength $H=240$ G on the dielectric constant of the solvent ϵ (in Debye); $[Py]=0.1$ mM; $[DMA]=60$ mM. Some of the points are obtained with single component solvents, propan-1-ol ($\epsilon=20$), methanol ($\epsilon=38$) and acetonitrile ($\epsilon=37$). Others are obtained in mixed solvent with methanol and propanol at different volume ratios.

more of an artifact than real, for at low donor concentration, the pyrene excimer luminescence accompanies the exciplex luminescence and hence the ϕ value is overestimated.

Table 1 clearly shows that the measured $B_{1/2}$ values have no relationship with the τ values, either in the case where a decrease in τ has been brought about by addition of quenchers or when τ is increased by choosing a solvent of lower dielectric constant. The observed τ values, of course, refers to caged luminescence exciplex but they can be assumed to run parallel to uncaged radical pair level broadening. A longer lived luminescent exciplex is analogous to a time window of longer delay, in which the magnetic field effect originates from the participation of radical pairs which have longer lifetime and hence less level broadening. This negative correlation significantly establishes the point that the increase of $B_{1/2}$ due to increase in DMA concentration as observed first by Weller and others⁹ and that due to increase in DMT concentration as observed by us¹⁶ cannot possibly be explained as caused by variation of the lifetime of exciplex or the radical pair. In the reported experiments with sampling time window at various delays the $B_{1/2}$ value for the system anthracene/DMA in CH_2CN has been observed to be increased from 58 to 67 G as the delay is decreased from 11 to 7 ns¹¹. There are also reported data that at very short delay time the $B_{1/2}$ value increases rapidly and becomes almost independent of HFI^{10,11}. These are very appropriately explained on the basis of the energy level broadening caused by the experimental constraint of selective sampling at short times. But this apparently is not responsible for the increase in $B_{1/2}$ with increase in donor

concentration which has been observed through both the transient triplet absorption and steady state singlet luminescence studies. The failure to obtain any direct correlation of lifetime of the exciplex (varied over identical range, 17 to 6 ns) with the observed $B_{1/2}$ values suggests that the change in $B_{1/2}$ on addition of excess DMT or DMA is probably brought about by direct environmental perturbation on spin rephasing rate rather than through the environmental influence on lifetime. The influence of environment on the nuclear hyperfine interaction through a perturbation of the electronic wavefunction has indeed been observed in Mössbauer spectroscopy of iron complexes, although the magnitude of perturbation is much less than that required in the present case. It may be pointed out, however, that in the present case the magnetic nuclei of the environment (*i.e.* protons) are also expected to be coupled 'directly' to the electronic wavefunction of the radical pair providing larger change in the 'total' average nuclear hyperfine interaction. Indeed, hyperfine coupling of ionic free radical wavefunction with magnetic nuclei of non-bonded counter ion is known in epr spectroscopy²⁰.

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